

The Misunderstanding between Schizophrenia and Clairaudience

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ABSTRACT: This research focuses on Schizophrenia and Clairaudience that is part of doctoral research for a Doctorate of Metaphysical Sciences at the University of Metaphysics. The mental illness known as Schizophrenia has been known for centuries. There are various symptoms associated with this mental illness upon which a diagnosis is based. The exact causes of the mental illness Schizophrenia remain unknown, as does the actual part of the individual which is effected by the illness. The most prominent and definable symptom of Schizophrenia remains to be auditory hallucinations. Another explanation for individual's being able to hear voices, is that of clairaudience, a psychic ability. Clairaudient ability has a positive connotation upon the ability to hear voices, whereas the diagnosis of Schizophrenia is most commonly treated with pharmaceutical drugs to reduce or eliminate symptoms. This paper involves information about Schizophrenia, how it is perceived and treated. It also discusses various views of clairaudience, and how it is effective and manageable. A new approach is required to the medical industry when individuals are being treated for a diagnosis of Schizophrenia.

BACKGROUND

This article came about through researching for a dissertation for the Doctorate of Metaphysical Sciences at the University of Metaphysics. The dissertation will include considerably more references and research. This brief article is from preliminary research, as findings were of great interest to the field of metaphysics and should be shared.

The topic is an important one to explore the alternative view of traditional medical diagnoses to a more spiritual and even shamanic approach, just as Joseph Polimeni has done. By exploring the definitive symptoms and traits of clairaudience and schizophrenia, similarities can be drawn, and important questions are raised. As there are so many people effected by schizophrenic diagnoses, and ineffective treatments remain heavily drug based, a new approach needs to be taken.

Traditional medical views of schizophrenia see it as a burden and are incomprehensive and not agreed upon across the medical industry. In the community, schizophrenia is also stigmatized, misunderstood and even feared. Schizophrenics are often associated with violent or erratic behavior. Once thought of as a split

personality, the understanding of schizophrenia and those diagnosed with it, has changed over time.

Joseph Polimeni describes the 'Schizophrenia Paradox' as schizophrenia's defining features which are not agreed upon by the traditional medical industry. That the system or determinants of diagnosis of schizophrenia are not universal, coherent or acceptable to the whole medical community. Polimeni states that there is a need to offer a new belief system around schizophrenia. This paradox of schizophrenia is used in my discussion.ⁱ

It has also been suggested since the 1960's, by Thomas Szaszⁱⁱ and others, that schizophrenia and many other psychiatric disorders are in fact not (or not entirely) medical diseases. That there are other ways to assess the symptoms of people who have been given a traditional diagnosis. The Psychiatric focus for treatment of schizophrenia has been on drug-based treatments. This therapeutic Intervention type has been around since the 1950's and drug-based treatment is now routine for diagnosed schizophrenics.

Clairaudience is not widely written about on its own, but rather grouped amongst the

clairvoyant abilities or psychic abilities and is therefore somewhat difficult to research. The ability to hear voices has long been associated with spiritual ability including shamanism, and spirituality gives a much more positive view of this as a gift not a burden. Clairaudience Is one of the many psychic gifts people possess. It is an ability which can be developed and grown if nurtured.ⁱⁱⁱ

Clairaudience is described by Pete Sanders as Psychic Hearing, like what you hear inside your mind when we self-talk, an inner dialogue. Sanders also associated clairaudience with telepathy, an inner hearing in words not images, as the voice within provides inner guidance. Sarah Wiseman^{iv} also uses the term Psychic Hearing, like accesses a direct connection to the Divine. These definitions are what the following discussion is based on.

DISCUSSION

Schizophrenia is, according to Alex Rice, one of the easiest psychiatric disorders to misdiagnose, due to the complexity of the brain and our lack of understanding of it. It is an illness typically diagnosed in the late teens to early twenties, with symptoms including psychosis, delusions and hallucinations. It is also an illness which affects the brain and how it perceives the world.^v

The main symptoms of schizophrenia have been thought by many to include delusions, hallucinations, including auditory hallucinations or hearing voices and disorganized speech or behavior. These symptoms are not limited to just schizophrenia but are also the symptoms of several other mental disorders, providing questionable means of diagnosis.

Those living in faith and religious communities offer a different view of the mentally ill. It has been said that spirituality and religion have no place in therapy for mental illness. Yet for centuries religious communities have taken care of mentally ill individuals. Boisen believed that schizophrenia could be understood as an attempt to solve the problems of the soul. The

medical Industry often does not take into consideration these beliefs or notions.^{vi}

Current drug-based treatments are aimed at decreasing the symptoms, including reducing or stopping delusions and hallucinations. There have been many cases of schizophrenia which suggest the individual was at risk of causing harm to themselves, but not others. Psychosis is also a symptom of schizophrenia, where individuals may suffer one or more episodes throughout their lifetime. Drug-based treatments are often aimed at decreasing the likelihood of psychosis.

In current research it has been shown there are numerous benefits to including religion and spirituality in the treatment of schizophrenics. These treatments have shown improvements in people's motivational levels and wellbeing. Further research would need to be conducted to determine the definitive effectiveness of treatments and alternative approaches.^{vii}

For a clear understanding of schizophrenia's context and its dynamics, we would need to look in to the studies of evolution, natural selection, medical history, anthropology and alternative views including those of the shamans and psychics, throughout history, and the cognitive science behind spirituality.ⁱ

Clairaudience is defined as the psychic ability to hear words or language inside the mind, from a source other than the individual hearing it, but just like how the person would self-talk or talk to themselves inside their own mind. This voice may be described as a person's higher self, or your subconscious, the voice of God, the Universe or All. It may also be the voice of Angels, Spirit Guides or other entities.^{iv}

Once a person has experienced clairaudience they will be transformed in many ways, spiritually, mentally and emotionally. One of the most common problems with clairaudients is that they struggle to understand the meaning of what is heard. This puts them in a state of confusion, easily mistaken for delusional beliefs or disorganized behavior.^{iv}

The voices, as they are described as, can be diabolical or divine, male or female, with infinite kinds of messages which can be disturbing or a nuisance to the listener. These voices and their messages are said to come from the Divine, God, Source or the Universe and can answer an individual's most pressing questions, like what is their soul's purpose or how do they heal themselves from the past.^{iv}

This phenomenon occurs globally and often the geography of a person affects their experiences. Some people naturally have stronger abilities of clairaudience than others, and this ability is often more present in writers, readers or people good with language and communication. This ability to hear comes from opening the mind's ears to receiving messages from the Divine.^{iv}

The practice of Clairaudience is said to have the ability to connect you to infinite energies of the universe. Through psychic and spiritual practices, a person can connect at will, accessing divine guidance for solutions to life's challenges. A person may view the Divine as God, the Universe or the Source, all are one in the same, and are infinite sources of knowledge and love.^{iv}

The ability to connect with a higher source, hear the higher self and divine guidance would mean infinite possibilities. Potentially this would bring positive, inspiring, artistic, creative ideas into the consciousness of humanity, would be infinite like the Divine.

Receiving messages through clairaudience may come in the form of music, hearing meaningful songs, through media as messages which appear to be specifically for, or hold true meaning to, the individual. These messages are considered psychic and are often subtle and symbolic. These messages may be considered as delusional beliefs by modern science.^{iv}

It is time for a reassessment of mental health and its treatments. How we treat those with different views, opinions or beliefs will shape the society of the future. If treatments do not change, neither will outcomes. Suicide rates are

high amongst those with a diagnosis of schizophrenia. Smoking and other poor health choices are also high among those diagnosed with the illness, leading to their poor overall health and wellbeing.

CONCLUSION

The categorization of people as schizophrenic is largely through the lack of understanding of the person, their background and their beliefs. It is merely a way to label, stereotype or categorize a person for no other purpose than to place them in a group of people with supposed similarities.

The defining characteristics of clairaudient abilities and the symptoms of schizophrenia have remarkable and significant similarities. From that which can be described or defined as delusional belief, as an auditory hallucination or catatonic behavior may also be described as receiving psychic messages, hearing from the Divine or carrying out spiritual practices and following Divine guidance or one's own intuition.

The alternative approach as presented by Polimeniⁱ in the publication 'Shaman's Among Us' provides an extraordinary view of the context and our overall understanding of what schizophrenia is. There is inconclusive evidence that schizophrenia is caused by any one factor, whether that be genetic or environmental. Yet treatments are standardized and primarily drug-based.

Clairaudience provides an alternative view which would ultimately change our way of treating people who are symptomatic. The views appear opposing, as the treatment of schizophrenia is to oppress, eliminate symptoms and numb the person to their senses. Whereas if treated as a clairaudient, we would encourage the development of their gifts and abilities to strengthen and gain an understanding of them.

Clairaudience provides a positive view upon the experiences which millions of people have had throughout history. The differences

between people's experiences of the senses, including hearing within the mind, inner dialogues or inner voices may be interpreted as the hearing angels, hearing the voice of God or the Universe. These beliefs harm no one, need not be suppressed or eliminated and do not require drug-based treatments but rather nurturing and understanding.

The inspiration and creativity of people diagnosed with schizophrenia, in media and the arts, is already astounding. Like the movie, a Beautiful Mind, these creative people with a variety of experiences live amongst the masses and have a quality life to lead.

The medical industry cannot agree on what schizophrenia is, what makes a person schizophrenic and how that person became schizophrenic. It's a term used to categorize people experiencing one or more symptoms, which may or may not be related to other determinable illnesses. This research opens the gates to the re-evaluation of terminology, categorization and treatments of those, not just with schizophrenia, but with any number of mental illnesses.

About Philippa Richardson

Philippa lives, works, and plays in Melbourne, Victoria, Australia. She earned a master's degree in metaphysical sciences and bachelor of metaphysical sciences degree. She also has completed certificates in many alternative therapies including Crystal Therapy, Aromatherapy, Energy Healing and Spiritual Support, as well as Chakradance Teacher Training. Philippa has worked in the special events industry for over 10 years all over Australia. She is the author of *Life, Love & Everything, Symptomatic Addict* and *The Real Events Industry: My Story*.

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